
Evaluating the Efficiency of Service Enterprises in Rural Areas

Nizamova Rukhsora Akramovna

*Assistant of the Department of Digital economy of the Faculty of Huma,
Resources Management of Samarkand State, University named after Sharof Rashidov*

Abstract: In this article, current economic reforms aimed at the effective development of a sustainable and innovative economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of the global pandemic crisis are becoming increasingly important. Therefore, in order to overcome this situation, a number of socio-economic problems in all sectors of the economy are studied and analyzed, in particular, the problems of production in our country, author's research, proposals and recommendations on this topic are described.

Key words: efficiency, productivity, labor productivity, services, raw materials, products, profitability, economic efficiency, social efficiency, employment, unemployment.

Introduction. As service enterprises develop in the economy, the approaches to assessing their performance not only evolve but also become increasingly important in evaluating the efficiency of service activities

Currently, there are various perspectives in many economic literature sources regarding the socio-economic essence of service activities. Some individuals within interactive communities seek to acquire material goods to satisfy their numerous needs, while others aim to fulfill people's needs by providing specific services. The main objective of such relationships is not the creation of material goods but the fuller satisfaction of the ever-growing needs of individuals.

Although service activities may be embodied in tangible goods, they represent the useful result of labor consumed directly in the process of work.

An analysis of literature related to this topic shows that, according to B.A. Abdugarimov, service activities should be understood as activities aimed at meeting people's demands. Various types of enterprises engage in this type of activity, including individual entrepreneurs and service enterprises with various forms of ownership. The result of their labor is considered a service.

Analyzing the definitions above, E. Engel's recognition of the law connecting consumption patterns to income growth provided a stimulus for research in this direction[6].

This research includes studies such as determining the elasticity coefficient of purchasing power concerning income for different goods and services, among other areas. For example, in 1968, V. Fuchs argued that one reason for the expansion of the service sector is the lower productivity growth in services compared to industry and agriculture.

V. Fuchs also asserted that employment distribution across industry, agriculture, and services is closely linked to the per capita real gross domestic product.

According to the "Productivity Paradox" developed by R. Solow in 1987, the increasing investment in computer technologies did not lead to a corresponding increase in productivity within the service sector. Another reason for the low efficiency of service enterprises is the low wages of employees engaged in material services. However, some types of service employees receive relatively high wages.

Currently, foreign researchers are advancing several hypotheses to explain the solution to the "Solow Paradox." First, the most common explanation is the imperfection of productivity statistics, as proposed by R. Solow himself[5]. Second, another widespread explanation is that the existing material service framework fails to fully account for "services."

David's "Postponement Hypothesis" serves as an example here. Despite the existence of various analytical solutions to the "Solow Paradox," none of them have been unquestionably recognized as correct. Nevertheless, in industrialized countries, current productivity growth statistics indicate a stable increase in the efficiency of service activities[3].

Considering the above, in our opinion, service activity refers to activities carried out on the basis of providing various forms and directions of services aimed at meeting the material, socio-material, and educational needs of the population, social groups, enterprises, and organizations. This activity is carried out with the direct or indirect participation of consumers in achieving final results.

Research Methodology: The research involved analyzing statistical indicators of service provision and consumption processes, which led to the development of suggestions and recommendations. In addition, during the study of the activities of service enterprises, analytical and synthesis methods were effectively utilized.

Analysis and Results: In recent years, the consistent measures taken by the government of our republic to support and promote small businesses and entrepreneurship, as well as decisions and programmatic approaches aimed at developing specific sectors within the service industry, have led to rapid development in the service sector.

It is well-known that improving the efficiency of social services in any society lays the foundation for economic development. Therefore, increasing the efficiency of social services under conditions of economic liberalization and modernization is one of the pressing issues.

The overall state of efficiency, including the determination of socio-economic efficiency, is of great importance. Socio-economic efficiency refers to the achievement of improvements in the social, economic, and socio-economic status of the population by making rational use of limited resources.

Work is reflected in the growth of human development, material and social well-being, and cultural and spiritual advancement. The higher the level of human welfare and development, the greater the socio-economic efficiency achieved.

In studying the efficiency of social services across economic sectors, correctly understanding and calculating its criteria and indicators is of great importance[1].

In our opinion, to thoroughly and comprehensively study and understand the socio-economic efficiency, which is one of the key issues, it is necessary to develop separate criteria and indicators for both social and economic efficiency. However, this does not imply that the criteria and indicators of social and economic efficiency are unrelated. On the contrary, they are interconnected, complementing and reinforcing each other.

If economic efficiency is not qualitatively calculated and measured, it will be impossible to carry out the tasks necessary for its continuous improvement.

The growth of economic efficiency is an objective law governing the development of any form of service provision, as the development of society demands an increase in the volume and quality of the goods produced or services rendered. It also requires greater accumulation for the implementation of service provision, transactions, and expanded repeat services.

A comprehensive analysis of the economic efficiency of service enterprises should not be limited solely to efficiency criteria. The criterion primarily reflects the essence and main tasks of efficiency improvement but cannot serve as a measurement or evaluation tool. This function is fulfilled by indicators of economic efficiency.

The complexity of the criteria for the comprehensive program for service sector development necessitates indicators that characterize its goals and resources. In our opinion, the service sector in Uzbekistan, like the modern branches of the economy, is developing rapidly. Accordingly, the economic efficiency of economic entities operating in this sector is reflected in the following criteria:

- Meeting the needs of different consumer groups with more suitable products;
- Ensuring the popularity of products offered by economic entities;
- Increasing the effectiveness of the activities of economic entities;
- Reducing relative expenses;
- Achieving high productivity in the sector.

These criteria are determined by indicators that reflect the efficiency of service enterprises. In economic literature, efficiency indicators are classified differently: by evaluation scale, resource utilization level, indicator significance, role in decision-making, generalization level, and other factors.

In our opinion, economic efficiency indicators can be divided into two groups: specific and generalized indicators.

Specific indicators describing the economic efficiency of service enterprises include indicators of labor resource utilization and indicators of efficient use of material and financial resources.

Among the indicators of economic efficiency in service enterprises, labor resource utilization efficiency holds a special place.

In our opinion, the efficiency of labor resource utilization can be broadly characterized by using indicators such as the level and dynamics of labor productivity (both in physical and value terms); average wages; growth rate of service volume per employee; the ratio of service volume growth to wage growth; and the results per monetary unit of wages[2].

The level of labor productivity can be calculated in both physical and value terms. In physical terms, it is determined by the ratio of the volume of goods to the average number of employees.

$$MU = \frac{Tm}{Xs} \quad (1.)$$

Here:

Tm – Volume of goods/products

Xs – Number of (direct) employees

The efficiency of labor resource utilization in service enterprises is determined by indicators such as labor productivity, labor return, and labor intensity.

Labor productivity indicates the number of services provided by a single worker.

$$MU = \frac{Tush x}{Sir} \quad (2.)$$

Here:

Tush x – Volume of services

Sir – Average annual number of employees

Labor return characterizes the volume of services provided per unit of one som of wages.

$$MK = \frac{Tush x}{MxF} \quad (3.)$$

Here:

MK – Labor return

MxF – Wage fund

Labor intensity is the inverse indicator of labor productivity, representing the labor expenditure per one som of revenue.

$$Msig'z = \frac{M.sarf}{Tush.x} \quad (4.)$$

Here:

M sig' – Labor intensity

M sarf – Labor expenditure

The relationship between the growth rate of labor productivity and the reduction in product labor intensity is expressed by the following formula:

$$MUo's = \frac{Msig'x100}{100 - Msig'} \quad (5.)$$

$$MSh = \frac{Musx100}{100 + MUo's} \quad (6.)$$

Here:

MU o's – Level of labor productivity relative to the base period (%)

MSh – Reduction in labor intensity relative to the base period (%)

The overall increase in labor productivity (Δ MU umumiy) in service enterprises occurs due to the growth in service volume and the reduction in the number of employees, and it is determined by the following formula:

$$\Delta MU = \frac{100(\Delta V + \Delta Un)}{100 + Up} \quad (7.)$$

Here:

ΔV – Percentage growth in service provision during the current period

ΔUp – Percentage reduction in the number of employees in the enterprise (if the number of employees increases, the percentage is expressed with an opposite sign)

In service enterprises, the proportion of growth in service provision (or the volume/number of services rendered) attributable to increased labor productivity versus the share due to the involvement of additional resources (labor resources) is determined by a specific indicator. This indicator is called the **formula for the share of the intensive factor**.

$$Iok = \left(1 - \frac{Uis}{Utm}\right) \times 100\% \quad (8.);$$

Here:

Iok – Share of the intensive factor

Uis – Additional growth in the number of workers

Utm – Additional growth in the volume of goods/products

To conduct a deep and comprehensive analysis of the efficiency of service enterprises, both specific and generalized efficiency indicators are used. In literature, generalized indicators include: profitability, relative cost ratio, asset efficiency, efficiency of all resource funds, and other indicators.

The ultimate social goal of a society that aims to create the foundation for the comprehensive and harmonious development of individuals is social efficiency.

The second key measure of social efficiency in the economic sectors is the reduction of consumer spending, which indirectly impacts the growth of social service efficiency.

In the service system, social efficiency cannot be measured by a single criterion because the measures and indicators of sectoral social efficiency are not the same. While the measure of social efficiency expresses its content and objectives, indicators serve as tools for measuring and evaluating efficiency.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In our opinion, the statistical indicators of social efficiency can be grouped and studied as follows:

1. Statistical indicators describing the satisfaction of consumer demand;
2. Indicators describing the reduction of service time;
3. Statistical indicators describing improvements in working conditions and the nature of labor.

We believe that the indicators describing consumer demand satisfaction include:

- The volume of products created per capita during the service process;
- Gross products created per capita during the service process;
- Indicators for reducing service time;
- The coefficient for reducing the time consumers spend in service enterprises;
- The time spent per consumer for the service product.

Indicators describing labor conditions and characteristics include:

- The degree of automation of labor processes (application of new techniques and technologies);
- The level of service enterprise buildings and facilities meeting modern requirements;
- The level of using advanced methods for organizing labor in service;
- The degree of advancement of technology, tools, and equipment used in enterprises;
- The qualification, education, and specialization of employees engaged in service work;
- The degree of organizing training, retraining, and professional development for employees needed by the industry.

If any of the above-mentioned indicators are used in isolation, they do not reflect the overall result. Each indicator only characterizes a small aspect of social efficiency. However, when these indicators are used together, a complete evaluation of the social efficiency of service enterprises can be achieved.

The measures and indicators outlined above can be used in evaluating the performance of service enterprises, conducting comprehensive analyses, and creating the methodological foundations for strategic planning and their implementation.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2018, "Measures for organizing the rapid implementation of entrepreneurship initiatives and projects in the regions." minekonomiy.uz, September 18, 2018.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 2018, "Measures for further development of the system for protecting the rights and legal interests of business entities." minekonomiy.uz, July 30, 2018.

3. Abdukarimov B.A. et al. *Economics of Enterprises* (Textbook for higher educational institutions) T.: Fan, 2010. – pp. 122-123.
4. Abdukarimov B.A. et al. *Economics of Enterprises* (Textbook for higher educational institutions) T.: Fan, 2012. – pp. 142-152.
5. FUCHSV.R, The Service Economic *National Bureau of Economic Research*, New York, 1968.
6. Solou R. "We'd Better Out" // *New York Review of Books*, 1987. July 12, p. 36.
7. <https://samstat.uz/uz/> – Samarkand Region Statistics Department.
8. Turaev, B. K., & Djalolova, S. Z. (2020). Features of payment of labor in the service sector. In *Імперативи економічного зростання в контексті реалізації глобальних цілей сталого розвитку*. Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну.
9. Saodat, D., & Hasanov, H. (2016). *Xizmat ko „rsatish sohasida ish haqini tabaqalashtirish va uning xizmat ko „rsatish samaradorligiga ta“ siri*.
10. Низамов, А. Н., & Мансурова, Н. Ш. (2019). *ФЕРМЕР ХЎЖАЛИКЛАРИ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ УМУМИЙ БАҲОЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ*. *Интернаука*, (15-2), 92-93.